

REDESCRIPTION OF SPIONID POLYCHAETE *Laonice junoyi* (Aguirrezabalaga and Ceberio, 2005) (POLYCHAETA: SPIONIDAE)

REDESCRIPCIÓN DEL POLIQUETO ESPIÓNIDO *Laonice junoyi* (Aguirrezabalaga y Ceberio, 2005) (POLYCHAETA: SPIONIDAE)

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ABSTRACT

Available type material of *Laonice junoyi* deposited in Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales of Madrid, Spain was examined. Several important differences were found with respect to the original description and so *L. junoyi* is redescribed. Differences refer to fusion of peristomium with the first chaetiger; notopodial and neuropodial prechaetal lamellae are highly instead of poorly developed; lamellae postchaetal both noto and neuropodia from anterior chaetigers (1-4) are suboval with dorsal edge lightly elongated. Two types of capillary chaetae were observed: unilimbate (not bilimbate) in two sizes and alimbate.

KEY WORDS: Iberic Peninsula, Spain, annelid, taxonomy.

RESUMEN

Se examinó el material tipo de *Laonice junoyi* depositado en el Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales de Madrid. Varias diferencias fueron encontradas en contraste con la descripción original y en consecuencia, *L. junoyi* es aquí redescrito. Estas diferencias van referidas a la no fusión del peristomio con el primer setígero; en que las lamelas prequetales noto y neuropodiales están bien desarrolladas en vez de pobremente desarrolladas; en la forma de las lamelas postquetales noto y neuropodiales de los setígeros anteriores (1-4), que son subovales con el margen dorsal ligeramente elongado; y en la presencia de dos tipos de quetas capilares: el primero unilimbadas (no bilimbadas) de dos longitudes y el segundo alimbadas.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Península Ibérica, España, anélido, taxonomía.

The genus *Laonice* comprises species of Spionidae with the prostomium anteriorly expanded, reduced peristomial wings, the branchiae from the second chaetiger are usually separated with notopodial postchaetal lamellae, and nuchal organs that extend posteriorly for a variable number of chaetigers; most species have an occipital tentacle. The *Laonice* genus has 35 nominal accepted species, and about 13 of these species to European waters (Arctic and the North Atlantic, Mediterranean Sea). Sikorski (2003) made a *Laonice* review from the Arctic and the North Atlantic region and summarized the results of five previous studies of this genus (Sikorski *et al.* 1988, Orrhage and Sundberg 1990, Sikorski 1997, 1999, 2002). In this work the author clarified some aspects related to taxonomic problems within this genus, especially about *L. cirrata* and *L. sarsi*; and sinomized some species.

Four species have been recorded in the Iberic

Peninsula (*Laonice bahusiensis* Söderström, 1920, *L. cirrata* Sars, 1851, *L. appelloefi* (= *L. maciolekae*) Söderström, 1920 and *L. junoyi* Aguirrezabalaga and Ceberio, 2005. Sikorski (2003) referred to *L. cirrata* with distribution restricted to the Arctic Ocean; thus, the records of this species in the Iberic Peninsula are questionable. It could be *L. bahusiensis*. *Laonice maciolekae* described to Capbreton Bay, Spain was reassigned as *L. appelloefi* by Meißner *et al.* (2014), who reviewed type material and considered *L. maciolekae* as a junior synonym of *L. appelloefi* Söderström, 1920. They also argued that Aguirrezabalaga and Ceberio (2005) did not examine the type material of *L. appelloefi* and that the characteristics used to describe the new species (*L. maciolekae*) are similar (quadridentate hooks and prostomial shape) and that the number of eyes is generally not accepted to be a reliable character. In this paper, *L. junoyi* is redescribed due to some characteristics omitted or erroneously described.

Laonice junoyi Aguirrezabalaga and Ceberio, 2005

Examined material

Atlantic Ocean, Bay of Biscay, Capbreton Canyon Date: 08/07/1988; position at the beginning and the end of the row on the sea floor: 43°42,29'N-2°18,71'W and 43°43,25'N- 2°18,80'W; depth 984-1029 m. Holotype (MNCN 16.01/9240) and paratype (16.01/9241).

Figure 1 A-N, Table 1

Laonice junoyi Aguirrezabalaga and Ceberio, 2005; 272-274, Fig. 2A-D.

Figure 1. *Laonice junoyi*. (A) anterior end, dorsal view (holotype); (B) same, lateral view; (C) parapodium from first chaetiger, anterior view; (D) parapodia from second chaetiger, anterior view; (E) parapodia from third chaetiger, anterior view; (F) parapodia from ninth chaetiger, anterior view; (G) anterior dorsal view of paratype; (H) lateral pouch in paratype; (I) limbate chaeta from anterior row; (J) limbate chaeta from posterior row; (K) capillary chaeta; (L) sabre chaeta; (M) hooded hook; (N) distal end hooded hook detail. Scales: A, B, G, H: 0.5 mm; C-F: 0.3 mm; I-M: 0.1 mm; N: 0.05 mm.

Redescription

Both specimens incomplete (holotype fragmented in three pieces). Bell-shaped prostomium (Fig. 1A) with rounded anterior margin and an inconspicuous middle notch, conspicuous in the paratype, eyes not seen in specimenes examined, although Aguirrezabalaga and Ceberio (2005) noted the presence of a pair of eyes at the posterior end of the prostomium. Occipital cirriform tentacle and pointed.

Short peristomium, forming low lateral wings, not fused anteriorly to prostomium nor to the first chaetiger (Fig. 1A-B). Short caruncle divided into branches from chaetiger 3, extending to chaetiger 6 (holotype and paratype); nuchal organs running parallelly to caruncle, reaching chaetiger 7 (holotype) and 6 (paratype) (Fig. 1A, G).

All parapodia are biramous (Fig. 1A-G). Branchiae from chaetiger 2, separated from notopodial post-chaetal lamellae. Only a branchia on the right side in chaetiger 2 (holotype, none in paratype).

Notopodial prechaetal lamellae are well developed in chaetigers from branchial region, in the first chaetiger (Fig. 1A-C) lower than subsequents. The following notopodial prechaetal lamellae with rounded margin, like a lappet, and dorsally angled (Fig. 1D-F), in the postbranchial chaetigers they are similar to those from the branchial region but lower. Subtriangular notopodial postchaetal lamellae smaller in first chaetiger, with external edge rounded and blunt tip (Fig. 1C); those from chaetigers 2-4 are suboval with external edge rounded slightly elongated dorsally, ending in blunt tip (Fig. 1D, E); in subsequents chaetigers are kidney-shaped, well developed in chaetigers 7-9 (Fig. 1F), becoming rounded in subsequent branchial segments. Description of notopodial lamellae in post-branchial

region was not possible due to poor condition of the material. Notopodial lamellae united across dorsum from chaetigers 10-12, forming low crests, only seen in paratype (Fig. 1G) (holotype poor condition). Chaetiger 6 with a cilia crest, noticeable in paratype.

Neuropodial prechaetal lamellae low in first chaetiger (Fig. 1F), on subsequents chaetigers high and distally rounded (Fig. 1B). Suboval neuropodial postchaetal lamellae in the first chaetiger with slightly elongated dorsal edge, ending in blunt wide tip (Fig. 1C); suboval neuropodial postchaetal lamellae in subsequent three chaetigers (2-4) with ventral edge rounded (Fig. 1D, E), the following lamellae is kidney-shaped; decreasing near chaetiger 20 up to chaetiger 33 (paratype) maintaining the same shape. Interparapodial pouches from chaetiger 8, observed only in paratype (Fig. 1H).

Unilimbate notochaetae capillaries, with estriate axe, subdistal and distally granulated, arranged in two rows, included those of the first chaetiger, Anterior rows shorter than posterior rows (Fig. 1I, J), all chaetae with the same structure, and alimbated granulated inferior chaetae capillary (Fig. 1K). Notochaetae from chaetigers 15 to end of the fragment are thinner.

Neurochaetae with similar structure and arrangement as the notochaetae. Sabre chaetae from chaetiger 10 (holotype) and 12 (paratype) densely granulate (Fig. 1L). Hooded hook tridentate, with two teeth over main fang (Fig. 1M, N), from chaetiger 31 (holotype), not double hood observed.

Pygidium unknown

Distribution known only for type locality (Capbreton Canyon, Bay of Biscay, Spain between 984-1029 m depth).

Table 1. Comparison between original description and this study to *Laonice junoyi*, referred to some characteristics. (PrNoL: Prechaetal notopodial lamellae; PoNoL: Postchaetal, notopodial lamellae).

Characteristics	Original description		Redescription	
	Holotype	Paratype	Holotype	Paratype
Peristomium fused with first chaetiger	Not	Not	Yes	Yes
PrNoL	Poorly developed	Poorly developed	Well developed	Well developed
Anterior PoNoL	Rounded/kidney shape	Rounded/kidney shape	Angled dorsally	Angled dorsally
Limbate capillary chaeta	Bilimbate	Bilimbate	Unilimbate	Unilimbate
Alimbate capillary chaeta	Not described	Not described	Yes	Yes

Remarks

Aguirrezabalaga and Ceberio (2005) described *L. junoyi* from Cambreton Bay, they argued that this species is different from other congeneric species by the caruncle and nuchal organ structure. However, some characteristics are erroneous and others were not mentioned. We found that the peristomium is not fused to the first chaetiger; notopodial and neuropodial pre-chaetal lamellae are high instead of poorly developed; post-chaetal lamellae both noto and neuropodia from anterior chaetigers (1-4) are suboval with dorsal edge lightly elongated. Two chaetae type were observed: capillary unilimbate (not bilimbate) in two sizes (both with the same structure), and a capillary alimbate. We agree with other characteristics (branchiae, caruncle, nuchal organs, interparapodial pouches, sabre chaetae and hooded hooks) described to this species.

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